

Table 3. List of included longitudinal studies with quality scores (PEDro scale).

Research	Item 1	Item 2	Item 3	Item 4	Item 5	Item 6	Item 7	Item 8	Item 9	Item 10	Item 11	Total Score	Quality level
[52]	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	8	GQ
[53]	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	7	GQ
[54]	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	7	GQ
[55]	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	7	GQ
[56]	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	8	GQ
[57]	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	7	GQ
[58]	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	8	GQ
[59]	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	8	GQ
[60]	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	8	GQ
[61]	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	8	GQ
[62]	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	9	EQ

Note. 0 = item was not satisfied; 1 = item was satisfied Excellent quality (EQ)= 9-10; Good quality (GQ)= 6-8; Fair quality(FQ)= 4-5; Poor quality (PQ)= <4; Item 1: eligibility criteria were specified; Item 2: subjects were randomly allocated to groups; Item 3: allocation was concealed; Item 4:The groups were similar at baseline regarding the most important prognostic indicators; Item 5:There was blinding of all subjects; Item 6:There was blinding of all therapists who administered the therapy; Item 7: there was blinding of all assessors who measured at least one key outcome; Item 8: measurements of at least one key outcome were obtained from more than 85% of the subjects initially allocated to groups; Item 9: all subjects for whom outcome measurements were available received the treatment or control condition as allocated , or where this was not the case, data for at least one key outcome were analyzed by “intention to treat”; Item 10: the results of between groups statistical comparisons are reported for at least one key outcome; Item 11: the study provides both point measurements and measurements of variability for at least one key outcomes.